

THE ROLE OF TEMURI QUEENS IN THE STATE ADMINISTRATION OF TEMUR AND TEMURI

Mavlanova Sitora Sheraliyevna

Faculty of History of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek. 2nd year student of Master's degree in management of state and civil society institutions

Abstract: In this article, the role and importance of women leaders in various fields of management in our society is increasing, as well as in history, during the time of the great ruler like Amir Temur, attention to women in society and their role in state management is given. The article also contains thoughts and comments about Timurid princesses who have their place and voice in society.

Keywords: Timurid period, the predominance of the principles of justice in the foundations of state administration, Bibi Khanim, Sharafuddin Aliyazdi, Ibn Arabshah, military marches, ruler, Timurid princess, creative work, patron of science.

Аннотация: В данной статье возрастает роль и значение женщин-лидеров в различных сферах управления в нашем обществе, а также в истории, во времена такого великого правителя как Амир Темур внимание к женщинам в обществе и их роли в управлении государством дано. В статье также содержатся мысли и комментарии о тимуридских принцессах, которые имеют свое место и голос в обществе.

Ключевые слова: Тимуридский период, преобладание принципов справедливости в основах государственного управления, Биби Ханым, Шарафуддин Алиязди, Ибн Арабшах, военные марши, правитель, тимуридская принцесса, творчество, покровительница науки.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bugungi kunda jamiyatimizda boshqaruvning turli sohalarida rahbar ayol-qizlarimizning o'rni va ahamiyati oshib borayotganligi shuningdek tarixda ham Amir Temurdek buyuk hukmdor davrida uning boshqaruvida jamiyatda ayollarga e'tibor va ularning davlat boshqaruvidagi o'rni va roli haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan. Shuningdek maqolada xususan jamiyatda o'z o'rniga va so'ziga ega temuriy malikalarida haqida fikr va mulohazalar yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Temuriylar davri, davlat boshqaruvi asoslarida adolat ta'moyillarining ustunligi, Bibixonim, Sharafiddin Aliyazdiy, Ibn Arabshoh, harbiy yurishlar, hukmdor, temuriy malika, bunyodkorlik ishlari, ilm fan homiysi.

It is determined by the attitude towards girls and the opportunities created for them. This, in turn, should be based on national traditions and, at the same time, universal values. It's not for nothing, of course. After all, the spiritual level of any nation is determined first of all by the spiritual level of the women of that country. The attitude towards women in our country has its historical roots. Our ancestors always they encouraged to value women, to be respectful and honorable towards them. It was not for nothing that our enlightened grandfathers said, "If a woman rises, humanity rises." This is old history To'maris, Saraymulkhanim, Nadirabegim, Gulbadanbegim, Uvaisi, Dilshad atin, Anbar atin, Zulfia, etc. witness his bravery on the way. The unique qualities characteristic of our mothers continue in the form of our modern women. After all, as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev said, "A country that honors its women

will be powerful"¹.

In the process of large-scale and rapid reforms taking place in new Uzbekistan, increasing the socio-political activity of women, ensuring their rights and interests, gender equality, protecting the family, motherhood and childhood, protecting their health, and developing entrepreneurship among women , creating new jobs for them, striving and support initiatives, the state policy on improving working and living conditions has reached a new level. Today, our large-scale democratic reforms as a result of the political and social processes of our women participation is increasing. The fact that the chairman of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis is a female representative, and the fact that female governors are starting to work in the districts is not only in our region, but internationally a remarkable phenomenon in terms of scale. In December 2020, our country was divided into parliament and local councils. According to the results of the last elections, Oliy Majlis Legislation 48 of the 150 deputies elected to the chamber or. Women made up 32 percent, 25 percent in the Senate and local councils. This indicator indicates that for the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, the number of women in the national parliament has reached a level consistent with the recommendations set by the United Nations. Currently, women in our country are showing their talent and potential in all spheres of society production. Our women also have a significant contribution in the development of the fields of education, medicine, science, culture and sports. Historically, our women and girls have been active in every aspect of society and most importantly educated, intelligent, learned and knowledgeable. As an example, we can see the role and importance of women in the administration of the Timurids.

¹ Mirziyoyev. Sh.M. Together we will build a free and prosperous democratic country of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent.: "Uzbekistan" NMUI, 2016. P-56.

One with Timur and Timurid princes a number of queens belonging to the Timurid dynasty among talented politicians, mature famous and world famous scientists growing up came out. We know mostly above the state in all states the ruler stands. This is in state management the rulers' wives are also invisible to power has. The Timurids during the creative works of the queens we can also see it in the field of construction. A history that informs from the old days social while scrolling through the pages one with men in all areas of the field the names of great heroes in the line is also a witness of the fact that it was praised we will be He is also passionate among women rulers, wise advisers, mature sages, great scientists and intelligent art historians have grown up. In the period of the Timurids, it was also in state administration women have a role. Many during this period architectural monuments and madrasahs in construction of queens place big Queens during the Timurid period it was very important in construction works.

There are many interesting facts about the Timurid princesses to see manuscripts and lithographic works possible about them. Sharafuddin Ali "Zarafnama" of Yazdi, Nizamiddin Shami's "Zafarnama", Ibn Arabshah's "News about Timur we know from his works such as "miracles of fate", possible. This such as in the works too the role of queens in state affairs, importance, creative work done is brought. Timurid queens about initially when spoken. The owner is Amir Temur's wife made Saraymulkhanim we can see creative works. Saraymulkhanim to Chigatoy ulus belongs to the Mongol khans of Kazakhstan was a daughter. When Saraymulkhanim came of age in 1355, Amir Husayn got married. Amir Temur defeated Amir Husayn and executed him 3 months later, his wife. He takes Saroymulkhanim as his wife. Owner Amir Saraymulkhanim's marriage after receiving the title of "Koragon". That is see the word in Mongolian translation if he does, it means "Groom", will give. Amir Temur Saraymulkhanim to himself without marriage before all considered the eldest of the queens, "Big

lady" or "Bibikhanim" title will be awarded². We have many historians that she is mentioned as "Bibikhanim" in her works we will see. In fact, it is a title given to the queen. Of course such to recognition. In order to be a musharraf, one must have intelligence, wisdom, and a wide range of thinking was a factor. This is a story about a princess highly perceptive of his time, shrewd, enterprising, and in terms of kindness unique the fact that it is emphasized. Saroymulkhanim humanitarian, a lover of the motherland, well aware of the political, economic and social life of the country that he is aware, wise in the affairs of the kingdom she was a woman who attended with her advice. Especially Saraymulkhanim for knowledge interested, sponsoring scholars was a woman. Speaking of this princess during the Timurid period there were many people who admired this man's knowledge.

Saraymulkhanim Amir Temur during the war too in the country construction works, landscaping to work head it would be. Military with Saraymulkhanim Amir Temur he often went on walks together. Historical sources are given in unison information than very clever entrepreneur Saroymulkhanim kingdom in management to the body came some his rationality in solving problems participated with advice. Amir Temur although he does not openly obey Saraymulkhanim his advice need felt. Saroymulkhanim when talking about. In the era of Timurids, a student in love with science-science was the queen who was recognized as a patron. Timurid queens are the first to be mentioned. She is the wife of Sahibqiron Amir Temur the virtues of Saraymulkhanim manifestation will be. Our historians said Amir Temur against Iran the siege of Isfahan when the

² Fayziyev Turgun, Timurid princesses. Treatise. Tashkent: Publishing House of the People's Heritage named after A. Qadiri, 1994, 40 pages.

march began extended to many, the army with food funds will not be enough to provide. Then Amir Temur to Samarkand Saraymulkhan sent a letter by courier will send The letter is short: "Army stock is exhausted, send dice" it was said. A great scientist, a wise adviser Saroymulkhanim then letter after becoming aware of the content of the letter "If your great prince has run out of coins, is your politics over?" he writes and puts him in the car. Amir Temur after receiving the letter, Saroymulkhanim is sarcastic. Think about it and think about it comes to a decision: slaughtered sheep, horse and collecting the bones of camels is a seal for him about using it instead of money issues a decree. Isfahan after the end of the war after giving up, he will exchange it for dice. That's it by using the bone as a currency provides soldiers with food.

Great respect for queens during the Timurid era respect is shown. Even abroad ambassadors also learned at the welcoming ceremony we can get. Waiting with foreign ambassadors in front of the ruler the princess is sitting. It follows that The respect of queens during the Timurid period we can find out the height. This Claviho also said about it in his memoirs as written in Samarkand in "Dilkusho" park. The welcomed ambassador is Amir at the reception. Next to Temur, Saraymulkhanim and veiling the faces of his other wives says that it has passed. 2 Even Saroymulkhanim. It is history that he also sponsored construction works comes in small pieces. Saraymulkhanim Amir permission to build a madrasa from Timur asks. After Amir Temur agreed, his father a pair donated by Kazakhstan sell the bracelet and use this money to the madrasa spends to build. Saroymulkhanim. During the construction of the madrasa, work often comes managers on construction says his thoughts. Built by Saraymulkhanim madrasa end of XIV century beginning of XV century in Samarkand madrasahs huge and

majesty different in terms³. The mature mudarris of the madrasa age appointed, they seek religious and scientific knowledge those who impart worldly knowledge Amir Timur too. The construction of Saraymulkhanim highly rated his work. Amir Timur himself is from the Indian campaign back upon arrival 1399-1404 years. To Saraymulkhanim etc in Samarkand "Bibikhanim" mosque is built. The Timurids value their queens highly is manifested by giving. During the Timurid era because attention to princesses is high indicates. Only Amir Timur his wife is not Saraymulkhanim, but like that there are a lot of enlighteners and patrons of science. The performance of the queens during the Timurid period. This is when we are talking about the work he has done among the queens, saying that I am Gavharshadbeg we have to pass. Gavharshadbegim Shokhrukh Mirzonani was a beloved elder wife. Historical of sources testimony according to Gavharshad Begim has a high taste, is intelligent, entrepreneur, happy, single-minded, persistent, good. There was also a beautiful woman in the chapter. Nature religious Shahrukh Mirza spent a lot of time in prayer and reading books. Kingdom and my wife is an entrepreneur Gavharshadbegim managed. Even Shahrukh himself admits to his wisdom, prudent in managing the kingdom felt the need for advice. To this end affairs of the kingdom are under the queen's control - was brought to his attention. Even on walks would also be with Shukhrukh Mirza. Princess high-ranking military commanders observed their actions. ³ This is the queen's wisdom, awareness of politics, implementation other Timurids also increased their work would be surprised. Queens during the Timurid era high qualified their state. Wise advice in management is also taken into account was taken queens during the Timurid era. His works were highly appreciated. Even the

³Fayziyev Turgun, Timurid princesses. Treatise. Tashkent: Publishing House of the People's Heritage named after A. Qadiri, 1994, 40 pages.

beloved wife of Jahangir Mirza Classic to the in India. The one built by "Tajmahal" is an example of this possible It is clear from this that the Timurids during to owners attention strong means that it was besides. The role of queens in the Timurid period is incomparable. Such a thoughtful intelligence the same no from owners Khadikhabegim, Shod Mulk Khotun, Khurram Beg, Mehrinisa Beg, Jahanaro Beg, Begum Zebiniso and other queens we say possible. In the East, such queens are wise, intelligent, and learned separate resident many of queens we can count. Such queens Only a few can be found in the West. Only the Timurid queens did the place of his work in the state policy, admired the whole east for his wise advice it is not surprising if he leaves. In every country the role of the queen and her importance in politics has invisible power. Even nowadays the role of women in state administration is incomparable. It is being implemented in our country and the importance of women in reforms very high evaluated is getting married. We pay a lot of attention to women in our country is being given. In public administration too and what women do remarkable. In our country, from attention to women and girls is increasing day by day is going President Shavkat Mirziyoyev and "Supporting families and women circle things more "Acceleration" decree to this is a clear example. Protection of women's rights and legal career in the country economic, social and political activities increase and health care and so on work in progress.

In conclusion, it can be said that attention to women has been highly valued since ancient times. It is still the case today to see that things are going on possible. It is also social in public administration. The role of women in life is incomparable. Even now, attention is paid to women to support them many practical works are underway. Even women are in Amir Temur's armyis said to have served. Arabshah so writes: "Temur there are women in the army and they are enemies with was in conflict they showed perseverance. A spear is thrusting, a sword playing and aiming with a bow more fighting than skillful soldiers they

would"⁴. It can be seen that women courage, bravery, and wisdom have been known since ancient times. Even now, in social life, the state under the management done being increased the importance of the role of women in reforms is noteworthy.

List of used literature:

1. Mirziyoyev. Sh.M. Together we will build a free and prosperous democratic country of Uzbekistan. -Tashkent.: "Uzbekistan" NMUI, 2016. P-56.
2. Mirziyoyev. Sh.M. Ensuring the rule of law and human interests is the guarantee of the country's development and well-being. -Tashkent.: "Uzbekistan" NMUI, 2017. P-48.
3. Mirziyoyev. Sh.M. Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rule of every leader's activity. -Tashkent.: "Uzbekistan" NMUI, 2017.
4. «On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026», Development Strategy Centre, Tashkent-2022. P-106.
5. Law of the republic of Uzbekistan on state policy regarding youth. Law No. ZRU-406. 15.09.2016 <https://lex.uz>
6. Fayziyev Turgun, Timurid princesses. Treatise. Tashkent: Publishing House of the People's Heritage named after A. Qadiri, 1994, 40 pages.
7. Ibn Arabshah, History of Amir Timur. A memoir. Tashkent: Labor Publishing House, 1991, 324 pages.

⁴ Ibn Arabshah, History of Amir Timur. A memoir. Tashkent: Labor Publishing House, 1991, 324 pages.